

FRACTURE CHARACTERISTICS OF PARTICULATE REINFORCED COMPOSITES USING DIGITAL IMAGE CORRELATION

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ABSTRACT

In this study, wedge splitting tests were performed to evaluate fracture behavior of particulate reinforced composite materials. Crack resistance was evaluated by using CTOD (crack tip opening displacement) and crack tip opening angle (CTOA). The particulate reinforced composites were tested under various temperature (-60 °C ~ 50 °C) and load speed (5~500 mm / min). Also, digital image correlation method (DIC) was used to analyze the strain field at crack tip. Test results showed that the fracture energy increased with decreasing temperature and crack resistance increased with increasing load velocity.

1 INTRODUCTION

A particulate reinforced composite material is made by combining various materials of different kinds so as to have characteristics or properties not obtainable with a single material. Due to recent advances in polymer and fine chemical technologies, particulate reinforced composites have improved performance and manufacturability in terms of physical properties and mechanical properties. Particulate reinforced composite materials are used in various industrial fields and have been focused on improving the manufacturing process by analysing mechanical properties [1].

Particulate reinforced composite materials based on hydroxyl-terminated poly-butadiene (HTPB) are materials exhibiting viscoelastic properties by combining oxidizing agents and polymer materials. Such a particulate reinforced composite material may crack due to the manufacturing process, storage temperature, external pressure, and the like. Cracks reduce the durability, performance, and stability of the material. On the other hand, the strength of the particulate reinforced composite material is not only lower than that of quasi-brittle materials such as iron and aluminum, but also has viscoelastic properties. Viscoelastic properties make it difficult to apply linear elastic fracture mechanics. To date, no method has been established to demonstrate the fracture toughness of particulate reinforced composite materials with viscoelastic properties [2, 5]. Therefore, the mechanical properties of the particulate reinforced composite material can be analyzed by analyzing the energy absorption ability of the fracture energy concept [4]. However, this also has many difficulties in determining the fracture energy due to the viscoelastic characteristics.

The materials used in this study are HTPB based particulate reinforced composites. Fracture mechanics test evaluation of crack behavior is essential because this material may cause cracking in the conditions of manufacture, transportation and storage. Fracture mechanics tests are an indicator for evaluating the structure of cracked materials. The goal of the study is to derive fracture mechanics parameters and fracture toughness data and to analyze the effects of temperature and test speed. Wedge splitting test (WST) was performed to analyze the fracture mechanics parameters. During the test, the speckle pattern of the specimen surface is photographed with a CCD camera. The crack tip opening displacement (CTOD) and the crack tip opening angle (CTOA) were measured on the basis of the images taken after the test, and the surface strain was measured using digital image correlation (DIC). The

fracture toughness test was carried out at various temperature and load velocities due to the influence of temperature and load velocity on the characteristics of the particulate reinforced composite material.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PREOCEDURES

2.1 Material and specimen

The materials used in this study are made by casting a HTPB polymer binder with a particulate reinforced composite material that is a combination of a metal fuel and an oxidizer. Fig. 1 shows the shape of the wedge splitting test piece. The shape of the specimen was determined based on the CT specimen presented in ASTM E399 [6]. The pre-crack length was 25 mm and inserted using a sharp knife. Since the strength of the particulate reinforced composite material used in the experiment is very weak compared with the ordinary metal, the wedge splitting test is applied because the compression deformation is locally generated when it is directly imposed on the test fixture.

2.2 Wedge splitting test

The wedge splitting test is a method of applying loads using a notch, a groove, a wedge, and a roller [3]. Fig. 2 shows the jig and specimen for the wedge splitting test. When the wedge is lowered, the roller is pushed to both sides and the breaking load F_s is calculated by equation (1).

$$F_s = \frac{1}{2 \tan \alpha} F_v \quad (1)$$

Here, F_s is the breaking load, F_v is the vertical load, α is 15° the angle of the wedge. The deformation size of the material in the wedge splitting test can be defined as the crack mouth opening displacement (CMOD). The CMOD is calculated through equation (2). The fracture energy can be obtained by using the area under the curve in the graph of splitting load and CMOD and can be expressed as Equation (3).

$$CMOD = 2\delta', \delta' = \delta'' \tan \alpha \quad (2)$$

$$W_f = \int F_s d(\delta') \quad (3)$$

Fig. 1 Configuration of wedge splitting test

Fig. 2 Static system of wedge splitting test

Fig. 3 Speckle patterns of reference and deformed subsets[7]

Here, δ' is the horizontal displacement of the roller, δ'' is the vertical displacement of the wedge, and W_f is the fracture energy. The test equipment used in the wedge splitting test was the INSTRON 3367-409 environmental chamber to match the temperature with the INSTRON 5567 universal testing machine. In order to analyze the effect of the test speed on the particulate reinforced composite materials, we selected three types of composite materials, 5, 50, and 500 mm / min, to evaluate the behavior of the cleavage load depending on the CMOD under static and dynamic conditions. The test temperatures were 60 °C, room temperature, -20 °C, -40 °C and -60 °C. Four test temperatures were selected at the storage temperature range of -55 °C ~ 70 °C and -60 °C, which is close to the glass transition temperature, was selected. For the wedge splitting test, 15 specimens were used, one for each condition.

2.3 Digital image correlation method

The DIC technique is shown in Fig. As shown in Fig. 3, a speckle pattern is applied to the surface of the object to be measured, and the image is taken to analyze the correlation between the pre-deformation state and the post-deformation state to measure the deformation rate [7, 8]. In this study, a white lacquer was first applied to the specimen and a black lacquer was randomly sprayed. I made a speckle pattern like Fig. 3. The images were taken simultaneously with the WST test and the CCD camera was used. Fig. 4 shows the image before and after the deformation of the measurement area. Equation (4) shows the correlation coefficient $C(X)$ calculated from the gray level value path in the measured image, and the position at any two points is shown as Eqs. (5) and (6) [9]. $f(x_i, y_i)$ is the gray value for point P in the existing image coordinates, and $f(x_i^*, y_i^*)$ is the gray value of point P' in the deformed image coordinates. In (4), \bar{f} and \bar{f}' are the mean gray values of $f(x_i, y_i)$, $f(x_i^*, y_i^*)$ respectively.

$$C(X) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^m [f(x_i, y_j) - \bar{f}] \cdot [f'(x_i^*, y_j^*) - \bar{f}']}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^m [f(x_i, y_j) - \bar{f}]^2 \cdot \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^m [f'(x_i^*, y_j^*) - \bar{f}']^2}} \quad (4)$$

$$x_i^* = x_0 + \Delta x + u + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \Delta x + \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \Delta y \quad (5)$$

$$y_j^* = y_0 + \Delta y + v + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \Delta x + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \Delta y \quad (6)$$

Fig. 4 Schematics of reference and deformed subsets

Fig. 5 Definition of CTOD and CTOA[9]

2.4 Analysis of CTOD and CTOA

The fracture mechanics parameters generally presented are K_{IC} , $K - R$ curves, J_{IC} , $J - R$ curves, and CTOD. Fracture mechanics variables are presented by several organizations, and there are some differences in content or regulation between standards [6, 10, 11]. CTOA can be applied as a substitute parameter to CTOD due to recent optical device development. CTOD and CTOA are shown in Fig. 5, and CTOD is measured by DIC along with crack propagation. The CTOA is calculated using the CTOD and crack propagation length and is given by Eq. (7) [9].

$$CTOA = \tan^{-1} \frac{CTOD}{d} \quad (7)$$

In general metals, the CTOA rapidly increases and decreases as the initial crack progresses and has a constant critical CTOA value. This does not involve complicated theories and is excellent in experimental accuracy and ease of use [12]. In this study, it is analyzed to simulate the crack propagation of particulate reinforced composite materials which exhibit discontinuous crack propagation by repeating blunting and sharpening.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Results of wedge splitting tests

Fig. 6 summarizes the splitting load-CMOD results obtained by performing the wedge splitting test at test speeds of 5, 50, and 500 mm/min at various test temperatures, respectively. The splitting load - CMOD graph shows that when the CMOD increases under all conditions, the splitting load increases and decreases after reaching the maximum splitting load. As the temperature decreases at each test speed, the maximum breaking load increases and it increases greatly at -60°C . This is because the strength increases with decreasing temperature, which is similar to the result of SEM analysis after fracture using similar materials [13]. At the test speed of 50 mm/min, the tendency was similar to that of the wedge splitting test of Na Seong Hyun et al. [9] and the maximum splitting load was smaller. On the other hand, the greatest increase in the maximum breaking load at -60°C is due to the glass transition temperature approaching,

Generally, as the temperature decreases, the polymer material rapidly hardens at a specific temperature range, and the physical properties of the material change greatly. Under glass transition temperature, it shows brittle behavior and at higher temperature it becomes viscous. Bohn et al. [14] reported that dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) of HTPB based particulate reinforced composites showed glass transition behavior at about -60°C . Also, as the test speed increases, the maximum splitting load tends to increase. The viscoelastic material with stress relaxation characteristics has a low cracking load when the velocity is low because the stress gradually decreases over time as the force

sustaining the constant strain is applied continuously. Therefore, when the load velocity is faster than the stress relaxation time, a high stress remains inside the object [15].

(a) Displacement rate, 5 mm/min

(b) Displacement rate, 50 mm/min

(c) Displacement rate, 500 mm/min

Fig. 6 Splitting load-CMOD curves from wedge splitting test

Fig. 7 CTOD-crack extension curves

Fig. 8 CTOA-crack extension curves

3.2 Analytic result of CTOD and CTOA

Fig. 7 shows the CTOD derived from DIC based on the image captured by the CCD camera. From the analysis of CTOD, it can be seen that as the temperature decreases, a larger CTOD value is obtained at the same crack length. Indicating that the crack resistance increases as the temperature decreases. The CTOD results at each temperature except -60 °C showed similar CTOD values regardless of the test

speed and similar to the test results of Na Seong-Hyun et al. [9]. At -60 ° C, the CTOD value decreases as the test speed increases. The higher the test speed, the greater the effect of the brittle behavior due to the glass transition, and the higher the CTOD value, the larger the crack length [9].

Table 1 Results of major strain contour at crack length 3 mm

Fig. 8 is the analysis of CTOA through equation (7). From the analysis results, it can be seen that the unstable region appears at the beginning and the cracks converge to the stable region after advancing about 5 mm. The results of CTOA showed similar tendency to that of CTOD. The higher the temperature, the higher the CTOA value and the similar result regardless of the test speed. Compared to the CTOD results at -60 °C, CTOD results showed similar tendency.

3.3 Analytic result of DIC

Table 1 shows the results of the strain field analysis for crack lengths of 3 mm in each experimental condition using the DIC technique. From Table 1, it is found that the strain increases with decreasing temperature, which is considered to have greater crack resistance at the same crack length. At -60°C , the strain appeared to be brittle due to the glass transition behavior. It was confirmed that the strain increases as the test speed increases at the same temperature. As the velocity increases, the stress relaxation phenomenon, which is a characteristic of the viscoelastic material, decreases, and a large strain appears to occur. At -60°C , brittle behavior was dominant, showing a similar strain rate regardless of speed.

4 CONCLUSION

In this study, the wedge splitting test was performed to evaluate the crack resistance of the particulate reinforced composite material and the DIC analysis was performed. The tests were carried out at various temperatures and velocities and the following conclusions were obtained.

(1) From the results of the wedge splitting test, as the temperature decreases, the tensile strength of the particulate reinforced composite material increases, and the splitting load increases, and the brittle behavior due to the glass transition behavior at -60°C is markedly increased.

(2) In the wedge splitting test, as the test speed increases, the stress relaxation phenomenon decreases, and the high stress is left in the specimen.

(3) The results of CTOD and CTOA analysis show that the two variables increase with decreasing temperature and show low values for both variables because they show brittleness at -60°C . The test speed has no significant effect on the two variables and shows similar values.

(4) As a result of the DIC analysis, the strain decreases as the temperature decreases, and the brittle behavior at -60°C shows low strain. As the test speed increases, the strain increases because the stress relaxation phenomenon decreases.

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